

Roman Science Inspired by Emerging JWST Results: [website](#), [proceedings](#), [video](#)

Session 7 live-captioning, Friday, 23 June 2023:

[Surveys of galaxies before and around Cosmic Noon](#)

Vivian U: New insights on luminous infrared galaxies from JWST

Our next speaker will be Vivian U. Who has a presentation on New Insights on Luminous Infrared Galaxies from JWST. Thank you. Thank you everyone good morning and thank you for coming to the last day of the conference. And I've learned a lot this week so I really appreciate that the organizers have invited me out to talk I also have to apologize to the organizers for not giving a talk that was organizing the emails that I was supposed to give because I have no idea what that means these days. So instead of going to be sharing with you some of our recent results on new insight from luminous infrared galaxies from a cosmic dinner. I would like to start a fight by showing this animation of Veeva, 114 which is the Galaxy with going to talk a lot more about during my talk they can see the image way the eastern component of this merger is hidden and of course when I flip it lo and behold the light comes through. And then click to show this to both an outreach as well as an astronomer audience to remind ourselves that legitimacy is so sensitive and it's very good for picking up galaxies from the early universe but also it's allowing us to peer through and we have not been able to explore the spatial resolutions even in the nearby universe. So this is the exciting part for me. Okay first I wanted to tell you all why we are interested in infrared galaxies especially within our JWST results. We start formation rates in the activity peaking around on this chart. We seen this version before and this conference with emphasis on the high end. With the uncertainties that is being rewritten by JWST on a weekly basis. But here I am focusing on what happens since noon. So if you break this down by the population you can see that by .7 or so the density is really dominant by these luminous and also luminous galaxies. and why did they appear to govern our activities in our past? So, in a local universe you use them interchangeably because that's what they mostly are and they represent an ephemeral but important stage in a galaxies lifetime. So, within this galaxy merger paradigm, not every galaxy may go through this process but when they do a dramatic change is introduced to the properties and you can see a lot of star formation activities being picked up as well as the black hole. This is all happening within this one and a half billion years or so, this is because when you get these gas rich galaxies coming close to each other in doing the cosmic dance really starts up the gas that gets fed into the center and is introducing a lot of extreme activities as well as black hole activities that are getting triggered in stirring up dust and as we

are processing this we see the galaxies make them look infrared, of course we also see it blows out things and that's how the galaxy may or may not end. So it is this process are the stages that I like to focus this talk on because not only do we care about how mergers influence galaxy evolution as a whole, but I also think it is interesting to think about these processes at small scales where we can eventually understand the physics with all of the facilities that we have. To understand this galaxies is the population level we need to put together population so, this is the goal of our goals collaboration. The great Observatory survey, and we've -- over the last 50 years or so, we've amassed a huge data that further nearby 200 that was selected from the galaxy sample -- and what I really like about this sample is that it really stands a wide range of properties. So I'm the one and the host extreme environments such as AGN and starbursts that are upward of like tens or hundreds of solar masses per year. On the other hand you have your normal star-forming galaxies and everything in between. So it's been interesting to look at these galaxies both as individuals and also at the population level. Now, I'm happy to say that our goal survey is not just a multi-wave survey where we have data expanding most of the electromagnetic spectrum but this year we also have multimessenger survey and of course this is completely outside of my area of expertise but I hear it that their neutrinos as well, but I have no insider information on the announcement for next week. But neutrinos are interesting. That is my plug. So yes, for this a conference JWST conference, I want to focus on the infrared parts of our cities, and these papers are definitely by no means complete although there is some surveys or data center but let's get into the JWST part of things. So our goal is to really investigate the connection of these nearby merging infrared galaxies and this is a catchall phrase, and kind of on purpose because we want to -- we want to dispel the spirit of our program to look at these numbers have galaxies with all of the instruments for science or verification purposes and to prove that all we can with JWST. So these four sources we selected for program, they span a range of infrared properties in stages. All of the observations were taken in the second half of last year, and a lot of what I've presented it aching from the earlier part of the campaign, we have so many ongoing papers as we speak, and we also have a general program at Geo one and a Geo to program where we are doing more specific campaigns to candidates while so we have a large program as well. So if you wanted to collaborate please reach out. There's a lot of data going around. So, I want to give you some stories about these three particular sources, but I think I am probably not going to have time to talk about this but will see how far ago. So NGC 7469, it is one of the cleaner mergers of the sample as you can see it as an early stage merger and the companion is about a few parsecs away 20 parsecs away, so we have the dominant sources within this nucleus in the southern part. And is surrounded by a star-forming ring by the parsecs radius. He can see in the images they don't look as dramatic or they look drastically different as these images are still making picture of the month at a time to come out. And for this audience, I won't have to tell you about how an IRI works, but were just looking at the center of 7469, so because of the richness of the initializer that we found in the MIC data here we are really focusing on the number of these in the channel one, so we have the best resolution. And here I'm showing the folks Max if I am to molecular hydrogen, and Oregon too. And you can see the ionized gas, they look very similar with most of the gas. Either concentrated and very centered on nucleus, on a very comfy star-forming ring. And it looks completely different -- and there's a little bit more spread out and sent her a don't see it as brightly in the ring but is connected to some of the inner spiral arms

that is actually traced by JWST as well. They look similar in the velocity mass but especially you might not be able to see these in the scales, but we do see enhanced expression particularly in the new molecular hydrogen that is giving us some indication that they are shocks involved. With the front lines that we are now proving we have access to these high organization potential criminal lines. When I really like about it is that this line has a potential of upward TV so they really just activities that are unambiguous so here I've divided up whatever called the nucleus in ring to extract these different spectra so you can see the magnesium pipeline F5.6 Mike -- there's a very clear symmetry indicating to us that there is a present of a highly iron eyes wind driven by the AGN. Emily airmails who is looking this at all of the MIS data, he actually found this symmetric profile and all of the lines not just in this one. And it is very clear that the line profile is different between the high and low species. And also the molecular lines is also very narrow as well. So, we have looked at the full attack lines iodized line. Are we seeing a decelerating stratified outflow, and is calculated the mass outflow rate in the black flow accretion rate based on 0.04 and I'll come back slides. Since the scenario would put forth for this galaxies that we are seeing a highly itemized when that is coming towards us and is consistent with some of the large-scale widescale optical data that other folks have looked at and now were able to trace all the way down to the center, and this is depositing energy into the dense medium surrounding it and part of it is that because of the orientation of the system they are actually not too much interaction with the ring around it, as we explore the properties around the ring we really don't see it in the discernible differences. But Thomas was interested in the great distribution so he looked at this in particular here, and we've been looking at the 2 microns, and he did a bunch of circular apertures but this is a little bit complicated, but is when he looked at the different regions and the pH ratio of the Neo line concessions, is that he found a distribution farther away around the ring, but as you get closer and closer to the nucleus you see the rings. So this is suggesting that perhaps the radiation field near the gym I might beach during the smiling -- right now we're doing follow-up work looking at the nearest data for this galaxy looking at the different lines in the longer rings in the nucleus. And she has better resolution with new spec, and she seen some structure in the velocity field. So she is focusing on the combination line. So she did a really simple model to remove the rotation and she found in the residuals that there might be these potentially spiral structures left in the residual map. So we are tentatively calling this an info, and if this is indeed an inflow she calculated a mass and rate and these are orders of magnitude bigger. So if this is indeed what is happening, where having evidence that there is only for gas to pick up an essential parsecs region. Thomas who was a postdoc in Hiroshima, he's been looking at the imaging aspects of 7469, so combining the infrared, and the other infrared colors, he found a lot of new very dusty sources on the ring and he is able to use a color diagram to very young Stella populations increasing what we found in the galaxies of the young cell population is threefold. So, let me switch to this request -- and you've seen this before. I my titles right here is the 814 MH where you can actually see some of the large-scale title skills that are seen in nature, it is really need to kind of quantify the merger. Reminding us that these are not just processes but just mergers that are happening. So here are the images again, so here we are looking at the infrared imaging, where in this previously dust obscured region he's able to resolve the bright points down to multiple sources which we are calling the Northeast core in the southwest corner. And to interesting thing is to figure out where the black hole -- if one of these might be the black so which one is it. Sometimes, looking at galaxies and

think about bar codes that should not be that hard, but it's a nontrivial quest to figure out with a black hole might be. This is often not at the center. So Jeff Rich was looking into the spectral city of this galaxy. So when you looked at the infrared MIS spectral city, he found out that the southwest core was deeply embedded. So here we are showing the new spec data for the Northeast -- the the red is the Northeast going to yell at the southwest core. So this looking at the 3.3 features calculating equivalent which that he combined in colors in order to use the diagnostics any found in ambiguously that the Northeast coursing is in the region in the Southwest and they AGN dominated region. So this came as a surprise to us because this was the reverse of the nature of what we are distilled previous literature. Also there is no coronal signature. We don't see any lines and will be called the southwest core they seem to be dominated. We don't -- at least I don't think I fully understand what that means yet. But you. Shoshana Langdon who is a postdoc at human mass, he has been looking at the star clusters with their near cam imaging. So similar to what he had done, he'd also use these color-coded diagrams to find that there is actually a population of very red and dusty sources that are equivalent to less than 3 million years old, any firm that there are color-coordinated in this overlap region between the interaction fronts of the two galaxies. So with that he was able to place on this H distribution, you know these really young sources that gives us a really -- when combined with results of the order in population is really steep gradients in this same level at the ten a opposed to some of the galaxies they did a comparison of. So, this is really providing evidence that these distribution swaps for young massive clusters are found in the starbursts and merging galaxies. And then, my other colleague Justin, was correlating some of the results with large-scale gas that we see in these mergers. So here he is making use of large-scale wide field data where we are looking at low zero two lines and we find that the gas is going all the way out to at least ten killer parsecs from when the stars are. With enough clients, we can do that diagrams and we can find that both the identified clusters as well as the young clusters that Sean was finding, is that they do correlate with what we are seeing in the grave mission which is in the H to reach them. So dominated all the way out to tens ten killer parsecs or so. Okay, I will squeeze it and I'm sorry. So this is actually just one result that was really cool as well. So this merger was similar to the VV114, and we can see that this is also a clear interaction with at least two and by people say they might theorize there's three galaxies are going on. In the infrared and he says you look at it from the other Spitzer, it's coming from this region. And it's contributing to the infrared emissions. And of course will be have it we are were able to localize that admission into one of these points that were previously resolved by HST. And it is believe in this one of my colleagues has been leading this, she believes that D1 is responsible for the 70% admission mir omission in this resort. And we wonder what this is if it's a black hole or not? She looked even with infrared colors and unfortunately the conclusion is not as conclusive as we would like. Because D1 is falling in between will be called the starbursts and they region but, we find that she will seems to be following in the same region so maybe the buckle is here I do not know. But I can't she's looking to the spectroscopy, but I think we don't see the coronal emission yet. When Archer was going on. But that's another mystery we have to solve. So, now I would like to switch directions to talking a little bit about real men. But before I get started on this last part of my talk, I actually wanted to at this site because of the sum of the inspirational conversations that have had on Wednesday with my group about topics three -- so I wanted to do a picture or facilitate some of the conversations and discussions this afternoon that I

unfortunately have to miss. Our topic was kind of concerning how do we craft these general surveys that could maximize the overall legacy of the Roman data, and so, I have to confess when I was a grad student in Hawaii, I was extremely privileged to have access to some of the world's finest ground-based facilities. In the wailing to think about this is okay when we can do without these telescopes in the data weather permitting, but it actually took me a few years to learn to switch my thinking around to think about a size question I wanted to get answered to go after it with the data that we could get. So, I find myself back into this to circle thinking about the data and will begin do with the sign. So I think it's actually important to think about this in both directions because let's face it, we kept looking with one or two successful proposals, but we are not necessarily going to get all of the proposals that we want. So a lot of times it had to rely on the data sentencing and find these fantastic surveys that are coming online. So we need to set think about a science based on the data that is available to us so, with this mind-set I'm just going to touch very briefly on a few topics that I think will be interesting in terms of overwhelming synergy. So, what I think of Roman surveys which again I learned a lot about this week, I think about the statistics right -- and this is where we can do not just 200 galaxies, but you can tell me the number. And I think that with the high resolution in deep imaging we are really going to get all of the bright admission from the past shall surveys. Looking to see them everywhere. This is my bias. Within a see them everywhere. So we really sell some hints of it at the high rise shift and other high-res shift results that perhaps these mergers are actually more important than we might have previously given them credit for. So I'm hoping that will be have the service within a see them everywhere. And with this resolution make enough to see the mergers, but we can actually see the massive black holes, and I'm not in his cause and then the Hg for now but I suspect that some of these will still be hidden in obscurity, but I definitely want to defend them with infrared spectroscopy. But I think that these parsecs that we can then begin looking at the detailed observation in an area that is I am very excited about. And also with all of these imaging data, especially going to the infrared, I think you can do very detailed studies and a lot of galaxies. To similar to what Sean was finding, and being able to characterize all of this stellar populations, but also enabling us to do result SPE deeds. For a large number of galaxies. And I want to give a kick plug to my master student who started his PhD at ENU, he started this month and he was focusing on a center with high-resolution multiband data, but I think that we can do that for the whole galaxy it, especially for mergers, where things might be a little bit more ambiguous and how these processes are smashed together. And having the data points from JW would be fantastic to find any of scared sources. Lastly, I am not an expert in these events, but I heard that tea TEs, they are exciting to me, and you get a good resource for them, and what other people have found it in one, and share them with cases for. So I'm sure with the dynamical aspects of some of the upcoming Roman surveys we can definitely find a lot more of these things. Especially with the extreme environments in these galaxies that were talking about. So with that I will quickly summarize with the campaign that we found a lot of cough inflows and outflows and capacities in all happening with what we need it with Tyler's solution to disentangle, but the colors and spectroscopy have been really helpful in telling us about all the embedded nature of these things, although I'll have to say some of the ministries are still out there we still need a little bit more time to understand in my data to understand. So with all of the new data coming hopefully can study these processes at different stages of the merger and

to constrain and feed them models and such. But the real statistics will come from Roman. So now I will leave a mess of final slide and now answer some questions thank you.

Before any questions? Thank you for a beautiful talk, something to ask you more about 96 in particular, but you showed this beautiful imaging, but I want to ask you about this choice of -- yes this one. So, do you also have MIS for this particular region? And then, how this the 6.2 equivalent with this image. With up is a kiss for AGN? The short answer is I don't remember because it's been a while since they showed me this data. I do apologize, but it is to be determined. But definitely a good question who will look into that. Thank you, Vivian, this was really wonderful. So I remember before your JWST came up in degeneracy is whether be obscured and other types of feedback with PDRs and massive star and so on and now we have that, with Rome and we will be able to obtain in these infrared windows we previously had access to. Do you think now with the data in hand we can go back and with a more limited set of the spectrum be able to distinguish from other types of sources? Yes, the models definitely are sophisticated or maybe there's room for improvement are not a model in person, but you can really say if if you observe certain language above and beyond certain points these cannot possibly as the peer models as we know it so in that sense I think with the Jonas that we can in fact test those predictions, we can in fact tell. Now, why there are no Chronos lines in those things we think, I don't know. Maybe we need far more introspective but that's a good question, thank you. Okay, I think it is time to move on to our next speaker. Thank you.

Jasleen Matharu: Galaxies evolution with space-based slitless spectroscopy, past, present, and Roman

Okay, our second speaker will be Jasleen Matharu who will tell us about Galaxies Evolution with Space-Based Slitless Spectroscopy: Past, Present, and Roman. Thank you. So I really like to thank so today I will talk about what we have done so far with this mode of observation and what we can do with Roman. And also what we have done in forms of best ways to use on Roman. Okay so first of all what is space-based spectroscopy I want to explain what it is. We need the microphone for your online people. This little button. Is that better? Awesome. Okay. So come on the left-hand side you see an image from Y Field camera three over red shift one galaxy cluster and on the right you can see it's risen spectrum so you can see the chrism spectra are like streets in each of these streets are actually you can think of them like an image of the galaxy at every single wavelength with some overlap. And you can see the animation on the rate that goes through the chrism spectrum and compares it to its collapsed 1D spectrum and what that looks like. You can see there is an admission line there and in the chrism spectrum you can see that admission line looks like an image of that galaxy on top of the continuum. So the nice thing about chrism spectrum as you can process them and obtain galaxies so in the red Grissom you can get Alpha and the reason H alpha is also is because it traces young, hot, obese stars with lifetimes of about 10 million years so you can trace star formation on very short timescales and galaxies. You can then take the direct image would give you a map of the integrated star formation history of that galaxy or the stellar continuum than the end stellar mass and measure and that size relation to two different traces allowing you to get a handle where the star formation is happening in these galaxies in the past versus where

it's happening more recently. This is how I use space-based spectroscopy mostly but that it's not the only thing you can do with it. One of these things he may have noticed is you get spectra for everything in the field of view so it's actually a really efficient machine. So the nice thing you can do is for example I was showing you galaxy clusters you can confirm galaxy cluster members in one shot. For example here you see a selection of quiescent galaxies and these are galaxies we had spectroscopic shifts on the ground. We also had photometric redshifts you can see on the left axis and on the right y-axis we have the Grissom redshifts so what you can immediately see as you get three times higher precision in the redshifts that you determine when you use Grissom redshifts so that's the pink circle they are. No what that actually allows you to do is select cluster members from Grissom spectroscopy alone so you don't need ground-based spectroscopy because of that precision and this led to us increasing our member or cluster member example by over 50% of the original spectroscopic sample. Just to keep in mind these are quiescent galaxies so they do not have emission lines in their spectra that would additionally help you to do this red shift determination and you are already getting three times by precision periods obviously you'll have to show the star-forming galaxies which have this beautiful H alpha line and you get some times higher precision in your red shift determination so if you are out there and you want to get redshifts it's a really efficient way to do it. And the other thing is because again you get spectra for everything, you may find structures that we've never seen in the field of view because you may have used a slip mask or something and preselected to galaxies but I'm Grissom spectroscopy that's not the case. So here's an image of a Spitzer density image of three clusters and on top of that you can see points which show you different structures. The green points are actually the galaxy clusters themselves and all the other points or other structures that were found that were not found before. This is from a paper looking at Carina clusters beyond a red shift of 1.4. So please stay tuned for Guy Eleanora's talk he will talk more about this and this is his previous work. So before I go any further, this kind of science plus more that I will talk about is only possible because we have these excellent data processing pipelines that enable the science from Grissom spectroscopy. When I use the most is called the Grissom red shift and also software written by Gabriel Brahm Demott Brammer whose name you may know. Here, the laser works, here, and you can evolve with the direct image you get from HST so like I showed you before you get a direct image in the Grissom spectrum you can produce a model Grissom spectrum that incorporates the Grissom resolution and is an accurate duty model and from that you can get a 1D spectrum that has incorporated all of this Grissom resolution into it. On top of that what you can do is you can do model fitting to get your red shift determination, but also on top of that you can include things like photometry from other facilities that help improve your fit through the red shift or fit together redshifts and once you've determined a red shift you can actually extract emission line maps at the observed wavelengths where they are detected in your fit so here's a nice example from a recent paper I submitted that it gives you a whole wealth of emission line maps because you have these three filters on JW ST if you combined with the Grissom you can get everything pretty much. The other one a simulation-based extraction here at SMA and this where Grizli takes the morphology and combines it with your synthesis model but what SP does it actually assigns and SCD to everything will pixel and disperses it that way. So what you end up with his large pickle tables telling you what each of these pixels represent. So which object they belong to, how much flux do they have and which ones are contamination and so on and so forth. So this leads

to very pretty one-dimensional spectra and you can see how all the different positions and goals, their combined and this is a really nice H alpha line you can see here. So, to really understand the capabilities of spectroscopy enrollment and how that will compare we needed on one plot to understand what will Roman and give us that we didn't have before. So what I've done on this plot as I have taken all of the Grism's, I have taken their spectral dispersions, I've waited them by the resolving power and multiply them by a factor so you can directly compare them. So one thing to bear in mind is that all of these instruments should we say or telescopes have the same spatial resolution so you can compare them directly in that way. And what you might immediately see is that with, that was a spoiler, but when you can see immediately is that the Hubble space telescope's Grism's are quite low resolution and so our Grizli and you see the web near C.A.M. has very high spectral resolution and Roman is somewhere in between what we can achieve with these Grism's. So the kind of science you can do with these low resolution Grism's is you can make very detailed like I was telling you looking through the whole sloth of mission lineups here and this is some nice work from Raymond Simons in the clear collaboration where he combined a lot of these and you can very clearly see in some cases where galaxies are metal poor and metal rich in and verses out and you can do things like very detailed star formation profiles and you can compare them like I said to the integrated star formation history, here are work I did where you can see by looking at these plots of the star formation profile is more extended undisputedly so you can do things like this. When you have high spectral resolution which is very exciting because we haven't had that before in space, you can start doing spatially resolved Jenna Maddox and I think this is so cool. So this is a galaxy at redshifts 1.4ish and this is its H alpha match. This is the galaxy's rotation. So from the JW ST fresco collaboration so stay tuned for results like this coming from Grism using JW ST so as you can see Roman here has a similar wavelengths arranged what we can do with HST and web but you can see it's its resolution is higher. So, I will get into high resolutions also but first of all Roman's field of view and I think this is probably its biggest strength when it comes to galaxy evolution studies. The plot you're seeing here is the entirety of 3D HST's spectroscopy if you could do this you would see this spectral on here and here is JW ST near the footprint on the top here and this is Roman. So you can do the whole of 3D HST in one room and some people are like yeah, what's the big deal on this but you know, three HST took 370 hours. You can do it in a few hours. And again, people who are not in galaxies or like what's the point but 3D HST was one of the biggest galactic evolution like some of the most seminal papers we read about all of these fundamental relations came from this survey, you know? How many years that took or whatever you can get in one snap of shot which is ridiculous so 3D HST gave us 100,000 redshifts, gave us a census of galaxy evolution we need between Rich of 1 to 3.5 with high spatial resolution partially because of the wavelength range but it will give us 20,000 times the area of 3D HST and 100 times the redshifts hitting the high latitude white area survey, let that sink in for a bit, that is huge, you know? So that brings me to what is Roman actually going to do? What is going to do is it's going to do the high latitude white area survey, and as far as I know and I don't know if this is outdated, but it will be at least 1700 degrees squared, it will do near infrared imaging and full filters and slit was spectroscopy in one Grism over quite a long wavelength range and it will have these one telepathic maps we have been getting from HST and JW ST and we are going get 10 million HL from it, 10 million, that's just ridiculous. And then of course there's this 1.5 to 2000000 galaxy so to get an idea with these mass will look like we

have HST because they will look exactly like what we get from HST. Here are some examples of very deep HST imaging and emission line maps you can get from the Clare survey and you can see exquisite detail like the spiral galaxy and the H alpha is literally tracing so it's like IF view in. It's amazing. We have to think with 25% so the add-on Mike latitude is great because it will give us loads of galaxies but you can see from the plot here in the paper that compared the distribution of emission line galaxies would look like in a very small red shift range and what it compares to 3D HST so you can see 3D HST's flux limit was deeper so in the same patch of sky you have detected a lot more galaxy and got more detail in emission line maps, Roman is not going to go as deep in terms of the high latitude white area survey but a lot of the stuff you lose in depth you gain in statistics because you start out with these galaxies and get very deep profiles of whatever you want to measure. So yeah, back on that. Like I said emission line maps so this is an example those Artie done with what we had. What Erica Nelson did for 3D HST was in her paper she actually just took all of the H alpha and line maps so that was a giant footprint I showed you, took all of them and stack them and that's only 3,200 galaxies. Member we will get millions. She did this and she can measure the star formation rate profile, can you imagine we will be able to do with the high latitude studies of this what we can do with HST? Which is able to do here is measure things like where is the most likely place in a galaxy for a star to form? So we could get much stronger constraints on things like this just using high latitude white area survey. The other thing you can do is you can start looking at making statements on how physical processes tied to galaxy evolution and change their operation with cosmic time. This is a paper I submitted recent or current or recently which actually took Erica Nelson's and then I did it for the Clare survey so looking at H alpha versus continuing profiles with red shift and seeing if there's any trend of evolution and we found some red shift evolution surfaced but we have very limited data, right? This is from 3D the redshifts 1.7, you can see our error bars are quite large and you can imagine with Roman because we get so much statistics we can shrink these and sampled a red shift range even more finely to get the red shift evolution and things like this. The other thing I realized, and the reason I am putting it in my math at Paris so that if I'm wrong and an expert can correct me but what I realized recently as I think with Roman you'll be able to resolve the H alpha plus N-2 lines because we couldn't do this with HST wide-field camera three and slit was spectroscopy given the Grism's was I showed you in the earlier slide the circle to make you understand the resolution of the Grism's, Roman's resolving power was actually 461 and I did some maths and to resolve all these galaxies you need some resolving power which is lower than Roman's resolving power so this is true it means is for the first time you will actually have peer HL for maps. That means they are not contaminated by this and-2 and all this worked on previously on 3D HST has at issue in it so we always had to do some sort of correction to find getting rid of that contribution. The other thing that will be good about this is as far as I know it's really helpful studying AGN and ratio work that people who are studying AGN can do much more easily than they could do with HST and JW ST. So I talk a lot about Tootie because that's what I do but you don't have to just to do stuff with vision spectroscopy can also do things with one-dimensional spectra so this is a stack of spectra redshifts one from the Clare survey shown in blue and this same model fit in the red. When you can do is you can do model fitting to try to infer the ages and metal the cities of galaxies and this was done in the Clare survey and you can do it for loads and loads of redshifts and you see the age of red shift evolving and how the relation involves and you can see what I

will say here again this is a lot of galaxies but Roman is a lot more galaxy so shrink these aero bars, sample of this cosmic region much better, really pin down this evolution and you can measure these fundamental relations and really pin down the red shift evolution. You can also measure star formation histories of galaxies, so this is an example as well from the Clare survey and on individual galaxies so this may be something you want to think about for your general astrophysics proposal because the high latitude white area survey isn't as deep and this might be a reason you want to go deep because you want to measure star formation histories so you need very deep spectra. But the nice thing is you can combine it with the spatial resolution and make statements like are compact galaxies formed earlier which was this lovely result found by Vince Carpenter in the surveys you can make statements like this. This is my personal favorite. So I've been very excited about this because you have such a wide field of view that environment studies it's our time. You know? We can sample the whole range of environments just in one snapshot and we can start studying how the interplay of these physical processes at the boundaries of these environments actually relate to the whole ecosystem of this environment. For me this is really exciting because when I was working in galaxy environments, we have so many systematics because people would pick samples from a field sample that is in a different field taken may be with the same telescope but under different conditions who knows what other systematics or in a systematics or with environments today so if you do know one snapshot you remove a lot of that. So one thing that is there to think about is it may not be deep enough. Again the high latitude white area survey may not be deep enough to do this spatially with all the science you want to do in this case but as a follow-up to maybe go deeper with your own program in general astrophysics proposals. So this is something I did my PhD with ten galaxy clusters so we had that one HST wide-field camera three footprint I showed you and we had ten or so of those. And then in that sample we were only left with like tens of galaxies we could use in your measurement within clusters we can see signs of outside so they might do this and we have a small collection of galaxies in the end I'm spectroscopic slowly confirming from the ground, we stack them and found very, very tiny H alpha disks that gave the first indication that there is quenching happening in galaxy clusters, but we can go from indications to actually saying for sure this is happening and this is the way it's happening. And is it more important for high mass galaxy or no mass galaxies? We get a lot of information. Talking about JW ST a little more at this is a nutshell what we were Roman is going to do and so what Roman will find, JW ST will study in detail and verify. This is an example of a result I posted recently in JW ST nearest what took hundreds of galaxy only took 104 Grizli so essentially using JWST in 3D HST is around 1.4 and when you we pretty much got the same profiles of 3D HST but it took us tens of galaxies so you can imagine the things we see with Roman if we really want to study in detail we could do that with JWST and measure things like that. Again, detail, more spectral resolution, if more with spectral resolution is your thing, then JWST near cam is the way to go in slitless. So spatially resolved science, it blows my mind. This is a galaxy a red shift five this is its format and its continuum and Erika Nelson is currently doing a paper with kinematics where you can measure the rotation curve of galaxies at red shift five. This is ridiculous. So this is a plot I made with preliminary so I'm still checking misses and verifying the result but if you look at the first pass this is the service density I was telling you within the killer parsec but breaking into H alpha and the 3D HST and the clear results when you go to high red shift things are getting more compact and you can see my first pass were fresco results at 5.3 it really does look like

things are getting more compact but stay tuned to see if this H alpha versus continuum the relation we saw earlier actually holds up or it actually changes. Looking forward to that and a snippet of what you can do with JW ST Mayor can. I think this is the most important part of the talk which is whatever we learn from these that you have to be aware for when it comes to Roman. One of the things to bear in mind is that HST and Roman both only have a Grissom at one orientation or they use a Grissom. James Webb had two like for both instruments. What was nice is you can observe at multiple positioning goals with very little expense with HST you had to rotate the out of scope so that is something to think about. Out they observed at multiple position angles, some have more contamination than others. This can be shown in various works. In the collaboration showing this with wavelength and can contamination you can see from the data set it varies. And a nice way of seeing it in the middle of the screen here this is again from the player collaboration with the same source at three different orientations, you can see its Grissom spectrum and you can see there is a Grissom spectrum that has been subtracted from a different source, but I different orientations it either is closer to the Grissom spectrum we care about or it's far away. To closer it is, that's more of a problem because it becomes contaminated. So you can imagine if this was the only data you got, that is kind of ruin. So you want to do at least two or three position angles. The other reason you'd want to do this is we actually found in it leading to better construction of maps so this is work in Claire from KC and so on and you can see here this is a galaxy direct image. This is the emission line maps to see just single position angles at different orientations and you can see you don't quite capture all of the star-forming knots you would do with three position angles. So, if you really want good admission line labs, it seems to be suggesting at least three angles would be good for that here. It also helps out rule contamination that could be masquerading as emission line maps which is the bane of my existence. So, for example, on the right here you see this is overkill of course. Look at the crazy amount of angles but you see the emission line so we can be sure this is an admission line and in this example here you see this contamination probably from another object that is getting in the way but it almost completely lines up with the Grissom spectrum. You can imagine a bit lined up perfectly and this was your only position angle and he looked down here when you subtracted think oh it's a line and your red shift would be affected by that if your pipeline hasn't been able to subtract it well. It's something to bear in mind when observing with Roman, the other thing is please calibrate your Grissom spectroscopy across the entire detector frame. What we found with JWST is that it assumed to be constant around the frame and that is not of that later. We started seeing issues in our contamination modeling which traces were not quite lining up in what we ended up doing is measuring the wavelength point across the detector and finding variation across. So what myself and Brammer tried to do is measure and fit for this variation and create some new configuration that can be used to improve your data reduction in the spectroscopy when it comes to JWST. Contamination modeling is what I was talking about. It is a bottleneck currently in our data processing even for some of the smaller's HST and JW ST fields. So what I am showing here is again from the Claire survey this is one exposure. This is the continual model so how I was explaining earlier, Grizli models the image and you get a continual model for the whole galaxy. So this step here can actually be very computer intensive. You can imagine the view in one snapshot. Of its computer intensive now what will it be one Roman comes around? So we really need to think about this because there are ways around it. So what has been amusing for JWST near cam is

this filtering technique is these are two collaborations currently using it, I Geo and fresco, they do median filter by role here and what they are left with is the emission line periods or emission lines. If you want to do a mission line science, this is obviously not very computer intensive and that is fine, everything is great, but if you want to do continuum science like some of the things I was doing with the 1D spectroscopy quiescent galaxies if you want to do all that you can't do that with this method. So this trade-off with both methods and I don't know the answer to this but you can maximize the science out of this observing from Roman and why it's more important from Roman is that Roman's Grissom spectra in the JW ST we will have higher contamination rates then you see here so we need to think about this. I know I have more time but I will leave you with a summary of my points here so my main points are that space-based litmus spectroscopy spectroscopy is the most efficient. Please use it more if you want redshifts. Is the only observational mode that can simultaneously provide you with spectra and mission line maps over ridiculous amounts of galaxies now thanks to Roman periods bear in mind Roman's Grissom level similar wavelength range and spatial resolution to HST and JWST do better spectral resolution so that opens up some new prospects. And the interesting source that Roman will find like James Webb will study in detail so keep that in mind, and my worry, and I think Sunday we should really think about, is Roman's large field of view will be awesome for science but we really need to think about how we will process the data effectively, thank you.

Thank you for the talk. Do we have any online questions? No? Okay. Any questions in the room? Thank you, I am Ben Rose. It was a great talk. You discussed a lot about the Grissom and the high latitude white area survey. I was wondering how much you have thought and if you could comment on the time to main survey and the prism where you would get all of those role angles you were rolling, you get it increased depth at the cost of the resolution. It's not really something I think about, it's quite funny because I have done Grissom spectroscopy for my life I haven't really thought about 1D spectroscopy but I can imagine that being very useful for things like envision line studies but I don't know how people are currently dealing with the wavelength resolution whether that leads to additional problems if you want to do the one-dimensional studies and thinking about here, but if it doesn't end there is a way around it than that might be the way to go if you don't need large samples periods so going to that survey instead it will be worth it. Andrea? Thank you. So you made a very compelling case about stacking in order to understand the histories of galaxies and I was wondering if you have some golden rules for stacking in terms of survey strategies. That is a good question. So, I keep thinking multiple position angles because one detriment to stacking one position angles as you only resolve certain aspects of the emission line like I showed you and if you do that for your whole sample you may be biasing it in some way. But then in some way. But galaxies are oriented in different ways so you might be okay. The class to work I show, we only had one orientation for that. And we were still able to do a lot of stuff because all of every Galaxy cluster had a slightly different orientation so it was okay. I don't think they're big things and stacking you need to change for your strategies more about details. All contamination that the other thing, you want to lower your contamination rate they have a bigger sample so a lower contamination meat is better. Okay, thank you again.

Austen Gabrielpillai: ESpresso high-fidelity realistic grism simulations for Roman Space Telescope

Our next speaker will be Austen Gabrielpillai, and he will tell us about ESpresso. Can you hear me? Cool. All right. So hello, my name is Austin and I'm a post bac at the NASA center, inasmuch as I would like to talk to about ESpresso the beverage -- I'm not the biggest expert on coffee but I'm here to talk to about ESpresso, our simulation that we've been developing as part of Roman's preparatory work. Okay this one? Okay this one -- weight -- I forgot to click this. There you go. Okay so big thanks to the form of for gassing us up, so I don't need to do much on that, so since I have the slide, it's basically when you are expressing all objects in the field of view at the same time. So all of it collects onto the detector at the same time. In one of the ways we could do this is with the Grism which is a combination of the diffraction grating focusing on two of the objects behind it. So it is a great tool for identifying initial galaxies and finding and collecting a large amount of photos of but the downside is that the resources do contaminate each other and this can be mitigated through a variety of strategies. It spans 1.0 and 1.9 microns so makes a great tool for identifying retro seven. Which provides us with the motivation of why we have built our pipeline. So we came it was too close, what was to create a realistic market roaming prison for grants and image, and I was using real science, so we can inject our own oscillators. So that we can release our own data to the public. So folks can develop their own reduction code ahead of the response. So we have created our pipeline come up titled ESpresso, which utilizes three steps, the first is data cube, where we create all of our big data to create a data genogroup which is in our simulation type are Grism it simulation, that detects the coordinates, then we have a source injection where you can add your own synthetic sources into our foreground. And Python's bill from the ground up and we do utilize number and multiprocessing to make things compute a little bit faster. All right, so to talk about some of the various inputs, specifically the observational images we are using high resolution images of the cosmos field, and that is from the candle survey if of 0.03 per pixel. And we cropped out a little bit to move you know -- the way that tiling works, which gives us this image area over here with the Roman footprint overlaid on top. So we get to and some change with a detecting data. And they're also an augmentation map which allows you to identify which objects are which pixels are belong to which objects so that way we are only working with the data that we are interested in. And it's about 25,000 dot objects in this field of stars and galaxies going up to red shift six. As far as Spectra we are using the easy best fit STDs from the survey, and the original work fit 44 filter profile which were then fit this the templates but you can see this over here, that was the wrong one you can see this over here, and you can see that there is a number of both initial features. So what we do is we preprocess every SED. So we consider the components in the one-to-one Mike Rohn. Every sample them. One thing to note is that there are no SED's, so we had just fixed that in the preprocessing step. And so when we are creating a data cube, are processes that we use our map to only keep the pixels that belong to identify objects in the map. So that way we move other pixels that are not interesting. And that can be consequences of the model. And for each object in the field, we then determine the pixels percent contribution to the total flux, and that is of the object, and were using each object to multiply each pixel based on the SED wavelength to give us a monochromatic snapshot of the galaxy at that wavelength. So he gets kind of see that here with this little GIF that I've made. So

as we move to the wavelength we are multiplying that value in value to the image so I brightens up when we cross this cell line in the entire galaxy. And he gives us that snapshot there. So, moving on the meat and potatoes of this meal, is that we are modeling various orders and distortions so using this image data cube is inputs we have a sky to detect a polynomial were giving wavelength and we are using this tomorrow both and in focus 11 main science order, as well as two in focus of zero and zero and 2-2. This also wavelength dependent response function for a disorder where we model the cut off and there's also response will remodel and modify the response based on where it lands on the detector. So you can see here in this graphic that this is the same patch of detector for the zero N0 appeared, and the one in the middle and the two into down here. All of these are scale the same way you can easily compare to each other how far each component is. And so, we now also are able to show our full four by 4K simulation including all orders and distortions. In this is a new image Sega probably Kate that may play the game or rebrand 0-0. But right now we are currently using the PSF is a good approximation for the Roman PSF. So yes. You just see how crowded this field is where you see these bright stars in these dangerous objects in this patchwork over here. In copious amounts of omission right. And then moving another step upward, that is the detector of the simulation will we have basically done this using our input data as previously shown which then spans this middle column of detectors over here. And in this image we've also added some photon noise for the second and like I said, it is great that we able to get a photodetector's worth of data and then we have partial detectors over here. As a result of the partial detectors you see the off order spilling down over here. And then, some of the other features are these position-based chance points where one thing you can do is trading dissimulation to specify their position angle and the configuration file and selling this little one over here, it is a series of 25 position angle that was created for the metal detector we can see all of these sources did not contaminate each other, or uncontaminated or move into the field. So that way you can actually test what is the best position angle for recovering a specific source. We also had these other capabilities which are not shown because those are very hard to make a movie out of. But they are there. In one of the other big features that we have added is the ability to do source injection. So if your source of interest is not currently in this field,/for example, those who are interested in this that is not well represented, if given an image of the galaxy they want to simulate as well as the SED we can then create a image of however many galaxies you want to populate in the fields. And it creates a segmentation map, and it is all compatible with in our pipeline so that way it produces a chrism of just that source you want to look at which can be cool added on top of the noises simulation and then address some noise on top of that. And then there you go. It's your own little playground basically. To give a good example is that we have a bright star over here and there's just one line over here and then for another example is our initial line galaxy with various omission line with the couplet and then you can see how those features really could pop out well. Especially within the chrism. As for future work with JWST's, one thing that we are looking forward to is that the production of these large mosaics that we can use in our ESpresso pipeline. For example yesterday, Casey had mentioned how the web footprint can fit entire points in there. So getting that data would be beneficial to the community as a whole to working with this data moving it around. That way we don't need to inject as many objects because there's already already baked into these products. So yes, in summary, we have produced a realistic Roman extragalactic image. Both noises and with noise. And we have source injection

capabilities, and we are producing a message paper with the code bases and development and so is our documentation, and we are planning upcoming data release of the half of the Roman footprint which will consist of 25 position angles and with the others, are hoping that we can extend all of our products to upcoming in large and wide JWST mosaics.

Thank you Austin. Thank you those are really good talk. And I have two questions the first one is when you are simulating your grazing spectrum what configuration are you using? Is this a Roman one? Or how you would siding with the traces of four? And your plan for Cosmos I think is amazing but is there something you've already set up that can take JWST data and make it a simulation of it? Something we can you look at easily and play around with? Yes, to answer your first question, is that we have our own configuration file for when we create our simulations we specify what data cube are using it what detector you're using specifically in their will call you to pull from my library from polynomial's map of the sky to detect a trace for the order and if you want et cetera, et cetera et cetera, so that's the answer to make your first question, to answer your second question, we have not played with a lot of JWST yet, we've just been refining our images. And I imagine that our inputs, and our files, and the library is something that we work with in the form it for her own so I guess we can play around with the images. Or the-based prisms. Okay very good talk, so I'm just curious about the source injection. So, if I understand this correctly -- it's not that you had the SED, and the SED template you can basically inject anything into it including that say dwarves is that correct? Yes. I'm not familiar with the type of object, but if you have the image of the specific object you're trying to inject, and it is SED, we also have the source injection. But basically you specify how many one in the field and we are adding the capability of either using random positioning of these objects are just predefined list of the positions of the objects. In decades the input data classes that are then used for the rest of the pipeline which produces the adjustable prism objects. An additional question is that the images that you produce are detective based images, is there a plan for getting a final -- let's say a final image of a whole area? Like let's say a final composed image of the base area or something like that? Can you repeat the first after your question? Basically my question is how large it can be finally be composed to? If we have a wide enough image, we give Philip the entire 18 of all detectors. that leads us of some very difficult questions on how to restore our input data, and how do we get enough resources to do this commutation. Before the record we doing this in the supercomputing cluster and then making this fall graphic takes about 12 hours across one node of 20 ECP use. In this various things we need to do to extend to a full 18 detector will show him. But the the capabilities there, because you need to figure out the storage. Thank you page before we have an online question. Is there anything you need to do with machine learning? We have talked a little bit about applying machine learning techniques but none of us earned it machine many experts but we are happy to talk about that. You know on Slack and other forms of communication. Thank you Austen Gabrielpillai.

Eiichi Egami: The power of NIRCam/grism wide field slitless spectroscopy observations, early results and implications for Roman

Our next speaker is presenting online. So I am Eiichi Egami at the University of Arizona, and I really wanted to talk to the conference in person, but I could not in the end. So I am sorry for

that. But today I will mainly talk about the results from this virtual school be observation. The Poswer of NIRCam/Grism Wide Field Slitless Spectroscopy (WFSS) Observations. Enrollment does have a similar mode, although the wavelength coverage in this picture resolution and especially the area coverage is very different and are very different. But I'm hoping that what I talk about today, I hope it will be helpful to plan Roman and their observations. In a here man-made collaborators who are my students. Who just finished his PhD, at Cisco, so we worked on the commissioning of this particular building mode. And Greg who was my former student is now working on Roman educated with various rubber related information. So this first slide, this is actually the simulations, but the left-hand side is the near cam imaging and the chrism spectrum. So basically we just insert a chrism in the past. And then disperse all the lights in the wave of coverage of 2.5 and the resulting power is 1600 which is fairly high and this is various. This made this a very high resolution power and made it small and powerful. So what makes this particular mode powerful? Silas it a few major regions. The first is that unbiased mess, and a target selection. So for example when you use NirCam you have to choose targets based on the information. Before Grism the variation there's no need -- you just look through the telescope and take that data. So then also there are no slits so there are no slit losses, saw ultimately they are more accurate and also it allows us to achieve a very high spiritual school for completeness. What this means is that if you decide to target a given population of galaxies for example. With MSA we can only target a small fraction of those at the time. While they have it for many more sources. So this turns out to be a very powerful way to identifying the densities and so on and so forth. And also, Grism will produce data for the resources, with the speaker where he talks about how this is very powerful in terms of these regions. The kinematic of light-emitting regions. In the picks of scale is much smaller, so provides a better spatial sampling called the NirCam spec. So these points apply to the Spectroscopy the Roman Spectroscopy. It is the strength of split lists Spectroscopy in general. So these are the factors to consider also for the Spectroscopy. So then, why is NirCam/Grism so powerful for the studies? The simple answer is the large line equivalents of high retro galaxies. To this particular survey boat was that we well you know initially partly because Grism was inserted for specific purposes, but later on it was transformed into science mode. But another reason is that people did not think that we would detect many Irish galaxies with this. We would change the pictures the discovery of very strong light-emitting galaxies that number seven. So they were shown the galaxies on the left. So you can see the Mike Rohn is strong. And if you calculate the equivalent length of this line. It's like 1,000 long. So in the middle and show relation between the line flux and the brightness for ratio seven in the three line. In the upper horizontal distorted line, it's around 2,000 minus 18 emitters per second. This is roughly will be represent in prism mode in fresco. If you look at the dash line with the framework equivalent with a hundred on strong the basic liaison detection becomes 2 feet around 26 magnitude. Which is not a deep. And the line is 1,002,000 suggested by the strong hyaline detective emitters which are showing us the knitting through the dark circles. And then detecting these become possible down to 28/29, so this is a big reason why this particular mode became so useful in other words sensitivity was efficient enough to detect the large galaxy. Now the right-hand side, these are the estimated equivalent way of the actual Jay WST data. So the redline corresponds to the brightest sources and they explore seven to nine. So they can see that the brightest galaxies that these redshifts have both the equivalent of around 1,000 strong. When she to the middle panel. So, that indeed or most of the high rise on

the strong line. So that's what people originally expected. This is a key factor is that we found that the Grism was much higher to 40% than the three LipE production. Solano Purcell helped us Howie Rose galaxies. So the initial discovery of the six galaxies using this mode came from the commissioning data, and we were actually originally targeting these star, the center, the galaxy start. But the time was such deep enough to do texts six galaxies. So by itself it indicates that it must be of an abundance of meters of the high resolution shift otherwise ruinous even in store iteration. So we discovered this meters using the commissioning date or is only ten to 20 minutes for filter. So this was a heroic effort to distract these galaxies from the data sent but it was successful. And then, based on this data it became clear that the line functions in high redshifts, it's -- for example the function panel is basically very similar to redshifts to from redshifts six, very little evolution, in the case is similar for zero three, this seems to be -- just ignore Reds shift eight because this is not a remeasurement, but if you compared to the six ended three, there may be an increase. But on the right-hand side, this is a dark lie in the middle in the upper panel and lower panel. And these are the model predictions in room detect in many more line emissions. You can recall that, the busy function is dimming very rapidly. In a high resolution shift. In the fact that it's more constant that indicates that the efficiency of these galaxies are much higher than the high redshifts. Which was a major result of this paper. You know I will go through other and more substantial Grism programs actually, they showed the strong interest in this observing model. And I talked about this back in 2016. In one of the meetings. In a think that's why he decided to do this. Ended targets the fields and you see a lot of detections in the left. They can also see the leaders in the line of sight. For example, it is 6.3, and there is some forming less than 6.6, with a see a number of galaxies to texting with the line transmission is high. So this may be an ionized bubble. In all three of the functions did not have large number of sources. So they were able to constrain better. those purple points, through their initial determination of Quasar, with overestimated the function so that show -- the stipulation in the functional lens is really constant from redshifts in region six. You want to remind you that you only have 4 minutes left. Yes of course, so the Hyatt quasar fields, and the upper wiped panel ended Lucille and Eric, you can see a bunch of redlines. And these are the line meters around the quasar. And on the right hand saying you can see the spatial distribution of these three emitters which are shown on the screen, so that one strength of reason in the observation is that we can detect this kind of clustering easily. And of course the same data also produces that beautiful quasar spectrum, which we talked to on the first day. In fresco, this is a blank survey and note program targeting Gustav who is North. You can see a bunch of initial lines. And as you can see, in some cases, we can extract lying and mission maps. In this one of their advantage of the mode I mentioned at the beginning. And independently, independent of the the fresco team, we've been looking at the prism data, you can see that these are the lying meters at multiple different redshifts, at 1.4. And 3.6. Each off of number eight. So it's a bit surprising that we did and do see a bunch of redshifts eight line meters and very, very. And also both north and south and north, we detected that silver density. In the left one was already published, but the right one is under review. There is a very luminous galaxy 5.2, we detected a bunch of redshifts which is shown as the data in blue. In the FO left of the right panel. And finally it also detected a bunch of broadband a GM. So this kind of surveys also very effective for finding a GM. For the sake of time, I was skipped and go through this quickly, so finally, this kind of data can be taken for example in the star humming region in our galaxy. We were actually

helping the ice age group, in the process of the data for them. In here the scientific is different so they are basically looking at a bunch of background stars, and looking for social lines at the molecular compounds which is quite neat. In the observation is very powerful for this kind of observation. So this is my last life, so these are the summary. In and people are realizing that this is becoming more popular. And I feel like studies of galaxies -- this would be the next focus of many studies. It's a bit tricky in the sense that in the prism data, that we have to break that degeneracy somehow, but that can be done in that way. And I also wanted to stress that this data is extremely rich and scientific content. So I'm sure that Roman Spectroscopy can show a lot of exciting results and discoveries thank you very much. Thank you. Before we can get the next speaker set up and we have time for one quick question. Will come looking online to see if there any questions. Okay, that case let us Tim Finke Eiichi Egami yet again. Thank you.

Gaël Noirot: Planning for Roman, case study of wide-field slitless grism spectroscopy with JWST

Our next speaker is Gaël Noirot and he'll be talking about Planning for Roman: Case Study of Wide-field Slitless Grism Spectroscopy with JWST. I'm about to do a dance presentation. [Laughter] A in an interpretive dance. I'll give you an extra 5 minutes. I am Gaël Noirot, sorry for the technical issues, but I will be talking about Spectroscopy -- Planning for Roman: Case Study of Wide-field Slitless Grism Spectroscopy with JWST, thank you for the previous speaker introducing the previous subject, so I hope you are now all experience in the matter. And I'm going some works that we have done in collaboration to get this data. So yes the previous speakers have also already mentioned how JWST has been very efficient in the facility like a wealth of science, using Grism Spectroscopy, and to give you some numbers here, it is also the strong machine. So the machine alone has more redshifts than any infrared facility from the ground combined. say yes it's a hundred thousand redshifts that -- one of the recorded order today, was the source. And it was confirmed independently in the lower lash redshifts and it was pretty good given the quality of the data you see here there is some new studies about this source but might be publishing three signatures with the red shift. And it isn't pretty interesting targets, and I think this needs confirmation. But it seems like this is working -- so yes, with JWST, we can also probe the high Rez universe, new shows to be efficient for that so this is just a few examples of high red shift galaxies that have been confirmed following in the F115 here, and in our own data which is a cluster field. And we also have an independent confirmation of the redshifts was a ready and 9.1. Enter the omission line there. But here we see the continuum and we did take the continuum and we can start to infer properties online detections and may be understand a bit better what is happening in this source, so this is very improvising for JWST. As we mentioned before you can resolve studies of the galaxies and doing their live show IMAP stated this is an example from 2022. And naturally derived the gradients in the galaxy a cosmic noon. and with JWST we really open a new red shift window thinks of the sensitivity of the instrument. anthem push the studies to higher redshifts. Which was not possible before and from the maps where you can do is you can resolve word is happening with our own team and our own observations. And then we discovered this galaxy called the sparkler because of all the little tiny dots here that turned out to be candidates. So they are red and very old from the history and colors that are kind of blue here in the middle of the galaxy and more young and

star-forming. But what you see in the map, is that those red little dots there, they do not show any admission, so that collaborates the global candidates. Until now. In its 1.37 where he detected thanks to the magnification of the cluster end.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

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